

Microservices based Artificial Intelligence Diagnosis System for Zero Defect Manufacturing

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Abstract—As manufacturing evolves towards high-quality and high-output production, the demand for intelligent, defect-free systems becomes increasingly critical. Zero Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) emerges as a key paradigm, relying on real-time data and predictive analytics to proactively detect and mitigate quality deviations. In this work, a AI-based diagnosis system is proposed as part of an integrated approach to transform quality monitoring from a reactive to a proactive strategy by enabling the early detection of potential defects. This approach considers representing algorithms for predicting product and measurement quality based on live shop floor data, and optimization algorithms for fine-tuning the regression models aiming to enhance the prediction performance. The proposed approach was applied to an automotive assembly line, and the preliminary results shown benefits in improving the results of the diagnosis process.

Keywords: *Diagnosis, AI/ML-Regression, Manufacturing, ZDM.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial production systems are undergoing a profound transformation, spurred by increasing demands for higher throughput, greater product customization, and uncompromising quality standards. In response to these requirements, manufacturing environments are shifting from rigid, monolithic architectures to more agile and decentralized systems [1]. Traditional centralized production models typically follow a hierarchical structure, where data acquisition flows upward from sensors and machines to centralized control units, which then issue directives in a top-down fashion. While effective in static and predictable environments, these architectures often struggle to accommodate the dynamic and heterogeneous nature of modern production lines [2].

In contrast, distributed architectures promote real-time, bidirectional data exchange among machines, control systems, and analytics platforms. These flexible systems facilitate autonomous decision-making and adaptive process control in the hole manufacturing process. As manufacturing systems become more interconnected, the volume, variety, and velocity of data generated across the factory floor continue to grow exponentially [3]. Harnessing this data effectively presents both a significant challenge in efficiency and reliability terms.

In a smart, interconnected Industry 4.0 manufacturing setting, diagnostic strategies move beyond simple fault-finding to-

ward a holistic, data-driven approach that integrates sensor networks, real-time analytics and digital twins. By continuously collecting and analyzing operational data—from vibration and temperature readings to production throughput—advanced systems can detect anomalies as they emerge, classify them using machine learning models, and pinpoint root causes through explainable AI techniques. Digital twins of equipment and processes enable “what-if” simulations to verify potential failure modes and test corrective actions without halting the production line. Coupled with edge computing for low-latency alerts and cloud-based platforms for long-term trend analysis, these strategies not only minimize unplanned downtime but also lay the groundwork for predictive maintenance and self-optimizing operations [4].

This study focuses on comparing various AI-regression algorithms into predicting quality variables as part of a data-driven diagnosis system within a manufacturing environment. Specifically, the research addresses the modeling and forecasting of critical variables related to car quality and measurement consistency in the body shop and final assembly lines of vehicular manufacturer. By anticipating potential deviations through accurate predictions, production teams can implement early corrective measures, thus upholding ZDM principles and supporting data-driven decision-making on the shop floor.

Building upon the latest advancements in intelligent and connected manufacturing systems, this work integrates predictive models within a real-time diagnosis system pipeline with model drifting adaptation strategies. The approach was implemented and validated on a real-world automotive assembly line and the experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of predictive analytics in detecting anomalies at early stages, enabling more efficient quality assurance and proactive process adjustments contributing to the broader goals of Industry 4.0 by advancing the integration of smart analytics in production environments, with the ultimate aim of achieving defect-free, self-optimizing manufacturing systems.

What remains in the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents a brief analysis of the related work, namely the existing approaches to perform diagnosis and predictive analysis in time series data in the manufacturing. Section IV-A presents

the system architecture for the diagnosis system where the prediction and optimizers are included and Section IV describes the case study, implementation and experimental validation of the proposed prediction approach, namely comparing the observed results and metrics with other approaches from the related work. Finally, Section V rounds up the paper with conclusions and points out future work.

II. RELATED WORK

An analysis of related work on diagnosis systems and their applications reveals that these systems are predominantly utilized in industrial fields, mainly in predictive maintenance and fault tolerance areas. Also, the fundamental concepts of defect classification and identification of causes, effects, and corrective measures are increasingly being adapted for industrial use. For instance, the U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [5] has initiated a project aimed at developing monitoring, diagnosis, and prognostic solutions for manufacturing operations, underscoring the rising significance of diagnosis in this domain. Despite this progress, there is no universally accepted definition of diagnosis in manufacturing. Some researchers interpret it as a monitoring challenge [6] [7], while others emphasize its role in defect classification [8] [9] [10]. In order to solve this definitional ambiguity, this work leverages a hybrid diagnosis system that combines real-time monitoring with predictive analytics. By integrating continuous data acquisition with advanced regression models, this approach not only identifies and classifies defects as they occur but also anticipates potential quality issues through predictive techniques. This dual strategy facilitates the early intervention and implementation of more effective corrective actions, thereby enhancing the overall production efficiency and ensuring higher quality standards in industrial processes.

Recent studies have increasingly leveraged regression algorithms and advanced optimizers to improve the quality prediction across various industrial sectors. In the automotive domain, Msakni et al. [11] investigated the use of machine learning models—specifically, standard neural networks, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, and random forest algorithms—to predict the quality of bumper beams. Their work demonstrated that while all models achieved comparable predictive performance, slight improvements were observed using LSTM and random forest approaches. This highlights the critical role of both model selection and hyperparameter tuning when handling time-series data in a manufacturing setting. Also their work showed mean-absolute-error (MAE), mean-squared-error (MSE) and the root-mean-squared-error (RMSE) as typical metrics used for evaluating regression algorithms.

Khandekar and Agashe [12] propose a real-time, data-driven framework for monitoring and fault diagnosis of process-loop components—specifically control valves and current-to-pressure converters—by harvesting high-frequency DCS historian signals to train simple linear regression models for calibration error detection and support vector machine classifiers for fault identification, thereby offering a cost-effective alternative to traditional preventive and

condition-based maintenance techniques. Li et al. [13] present a non-destructive, machine-learning-based framework for diagnosing and localizing open and short defects in 2.5D redistribution layers (RDL) and 3D through silicon via-RDL interconnect channels: they simulate defect-injected channels in a 3D electromagnetic simulation software to extract S-parameters and group-delay features, employ XGBoost for defect classification with perfect test accuracy, and introduce a high-precision localization scheme combining Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS) with a density-based clustering algorithm for outlier removal, achieving mean relative errors below 8% and maximum errors under 13%, thus markedly improving over existing methods.

In a different context, Ben Lamine et al. [14] presented a comprehensive four-layer decision-making architecture in a smart factory environment. Their framework incorporated a diverse range of models including a statistical method (ARIMA [15]), machine learning algorithms (random forest and XGBoost), and deep learning techniques (stacked LSTM and Transformer-based models). The study emphasized the importance of integrating robust feature engineering and data balancing techniques to enhance time series forecasting accuracy. Their experimental results showed how layered model architectures and systematic hyperparameter optimization can drive quality improvements in industrial production. Focusing on environmental applications, Mallika et al. [16] conducted a comparative study on water quality prediction using various regression-based models. Their work compared traditional regression techniques such as decision trees, random forest, and XGBoost. Furthermore, they explored optimization strategies—including genetic algorithms like Particle Swarm Optimization and sparrow searching to fine tune feature selection and model parameters, thereby enhancing prediction accuracy. This study not only broadens the spectrum of parameters considered in regression models but also demonstrates the potential of automated ensemble learning for real-world quality management.

These studies reveal that the choice of regression model and optimizer is highly context-dependent, with successful implementations relying on tailored data preprocessing, appropriate feature selection, and rigorous hyperparameter tuning. Building upon these findings, our work aims to create a system capable to adapt to different context and systematically learn. By comparing regression algorithms and optimization methods we want to further elucidate their relative strengths and limitations in quality prediction applications specially for diagnosis system, were the model outcomes can affect drastically the results.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

An open, modular, and secure platform for industrial cyber-physical systems aligned with the RAMI4.0 model [17] is proposed to implement the ZDM strategies, as depicted in Figure 1.

All physical-asset data from industry equipments are ingested in real time into the ZDM platform's monitored di-

Fig. 1: Micro-services architecture for the open and modular industrial cyber-physical platform. Adapted from [18].

rectory and picked up by a file-watching service that feeds a Type 2 Asset Administration Shell (AAS) server. The AAS standardized and creates a digital representation for each asset, using semantic models (static or dynamic) then it normalizes the raw data into industry-standard formats at a common endpoint. Once standardized, measurements are dispatched via REST POST to the AAS endpoint and simultaneously stored in a centralized data lake, which supports both event-driven analytics (e.g., change alerts) and document-centric queries. A suite of real-time analytics micro-services that performs monitoring, “what-if” simulations, fault detection and diagnosis. All findings are written back to the data lake and presented through the platform’s front end for trend exploration, analytical review and anomaly investigation.

One important piece in this open and modular architecture for ZDM is the AI-based *diagnosis tool*. This system is based on four core components: monitoring measurement deviations, evaluating and generating quality metrics, forecasting the quality metrics to reveal potential defects and gathering the possible causes, consequences, and defect solutions. Figure 2 below illustrates the architecture on how data is transferred within the system, illustrating the origin and destination of the data throughout the process. The highlighted micro-services represent the ones within the *diagnosis system*.

Fig. 2: Micro-Services AI-based Diagnosis System Architecture.

A. Labeling and Evaluation Micro-Service

The base system in the *diagnosis process* is the *Labeling and Evaluation micro-service* that gathers the measurement information collected from the shop floor with the thresholds defined for the process and evaluates defects and quantifies quality from both the product and the measurement process. Figure 3 represents this micro-service architecture.

Fig. 3: Labeling and Evaluation micro-service Architecture.

The *Data Handler* is a configurable, use-case specific application that interpret, analyze and pre-processes the data to assure reliability and prevent system breaks. The transformation protocol gathers both the measurement collected with the thresholds and turn the numerical information in a more meaningful categorical variable that holds the defect information. Figure 4 shows an example of the application of the data transformation protocol and also the *Defect Indicator* (D.I.) variable calculation process.

Fig. 4: Process for calculating the Defect Indicator.

The D.I. variable represents how far the real product is from the ideal product (without any conformity’s or 0) being calculated by evaluating and grouping the defect from each measurement. After calculating the D.I., two other variables are calculated the *current worst defect indicator* (C.W.D.I.) (If all collected measures were out of the rejection boundaries). And the *global worst defect indicator* (G.W.D.I) (If all measures were out of the rejection boundaries including the ones the measurement system could not collect).

Finally, the Product and Measurement qualities are calculated by the relation between those two variables, where the

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Product Quality is calculated by determining how far is the current product (D.I) from the worst product (C.W.D.I.), while the Measurement Quality evaluate the data collecting system from the relation between the current worst product (C.W.D.I.) and the global worst product (G.W.D.I.), this relation not only verifies the missing measurements and thresholds not established in the process, but it weight properly the critical measurements. Figure 5 exemplify the calculation from both the Product and Measurement quality metrics.

Fig. 5: Process for calculating the Product and Measurement qualities.

As both metrics were derived from the ratio between two underlying variables, the resulting values are expressed as percentages ranging from 0 to 1. These normalized scores provide an intuitive interpretation of quality performance: values approaching 1 indicate higher quality levels, suggesting optimal or near-optimal conditions in the production process. In opposite, values closer to 0 reflect lower quality outcomes, potentially signaling inefficiencies, defects, or deviations from expected standards. This normalized representation within information around the missing and defected measures enables consistent comparison across different production scenarios and simplifies the interpretation of model predictions.

B. Quality Prediction Micro-Service

After computing quality metrics, the quality prediction system serves as a self-learning tool into forecasting quality deviations from both the product and measurement system. Figure 6 illustrates the architecture of this micro-service.

Fig. 6: Quality Prediction micro-service Architecture.

The step-by-step breakdown of the prediction is detailed as follows: Firstly there is the *Data Handler* that serves the purpose of interpret, analyze and pre-processes the data to be sent to the buffer. The buffer temporarily stores product and measurement quality data and once this buffer accumulates B (Configurable via micro-service parameters) data points the training of a regression model is triggered. After finishing the model training the service predict the next P quality values, with the new regression model. The resulting predictions are sent to the *Diagnosis and Evaluation micro-service*, which analyzes the data and suggests proactive actions.

To capture trends and forecast quality progression in this uni-variate time series, regression algorithms are commonly used—such as linear or polynomial regression. However, due to variability in the data, some models struggle to generalize effectively. In this work, several algorithms were tested being selected one that is capable of having a fast training time and strong performance in dynamic environments within low prediction errors and adaptability that was also well-suited for the use case, as further demonstrated in the experimental validation section.

C. Prediction Optimizer Micro-Service

This micro-service aims to optimize the regression model applied in the *Quality Prediction micro-service*, thereby reducing the difference between the actual values and those resulting from the forecasting process, reducing prediction errors. To carry out the *optimization process*, it is necessary to store both the actual and predicted values. Figure 7 illustrates the architecture proposed for the *optimization micro-service*.

Fig. 7: Prediction Optimizer micro-service Architecture.

Furthermore, the adaptability of this micro-service makes it possible to select different bio-inspired metaheuristic optimization algorithms, including the Colony Optimization Algorithm (ACO) [19], Bayesian Optimization [20], and Binary Grey Wolf Optimization (BGWO) [21]. The result of applying the optimization algorithms are new hyperparameters, which are then sent to the *Quality Prediction micro-service*, to be used by the regression algorithms.

D. Diagnosis and Classification Micro-Service

The last micro-service in the diagnosis process gathers the information from the current product and measurement qualities, with the quality predictions and the rule triggering [22] results and aim to outline the cause, consequence, and possible solutions into three different processes:

- The Rule Diagnosis is based on the triggered rules descriptions and triggering specific explanation.
- The Label Diagnosis stores the current product and measurement qualities and pass through a Z-Score Based Classification model enabling a seamless validation of the current product for the final users around the results.
- The Future Diagnosis classifies the product and measurement quality predictions, also using a Z-Score Based Classification model, this indeed gives insights about trends in the product and measurement quality and also indicates miscalibration and non common deviations in the measurements.

All diagnosis results are systematically formatted into a cause, consequence and solution pattern. And in both label and future diagnosis a Z-Score Based Classification model was devised, it uses the last M product results from the *Labeling and Evaluation micro-service* stored in a local database, then the thresholds are calculated by Equation 1.

$$C = \begin{cases} APPROVED & \text{if } quality \geq \bar{x} - \sigma \\ ATTENTION & \text{if } \bar{x} - \sigma > quality > \bar{x} - 3 * \sigma \\ REJECTED & \text{if } quality \leq \bar{x} - 3 * \sigma \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

That classifies the current and predicted product qualities based on the mean and standard deviation of the last M products, then it defines the threshold to classify the product into APPROVED, ATTENTION and REJECTED.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

This section describes Experimental Validation of the proposed *Diagnosis Tool* to an automotive assembly line case study. Experiments are related to select the proper regression algorithm in predicting the quality variables, and another to evaluate different parameter optimization algorithms for the chosen prediction algorithm.

A. Description of the Case Study

The case study involves the body shop area of an automotive assembly line, where geometric measurements are collected by laser trackers in inspection stations, as shown in Figure 8. This assembly line produces approximately 700 cars daily, divided into three shifts, averaging one car every 120 seconds. The body shop workflow is organized into three automated stages, each with multiple workstations dedicated to bodywork, door assembly, and tailgate assembly. After completion of each stage, the cars are inspected at a robotic measuring stations to verify the gap and flush geometric metrics.

The maximum and minimum thresholds for the deviations represented as the tolerance, specification, and rejection limits

Fig. 8: Body shop stations sequence. [22]

are periodically established by the industry. In normal circumstances if most of the deviations surpass these thresholds, the vehicle undergoes a rework process that increases both the production time and costs.

In this sense the proposed *Diagnosis tool* aims to gather enough information to realize a Root-cause identification for the product and measurement related problems as they can verify key issues in manufacturing processes. But also enabling proactive actions to be taken via quality evaluation and defect indication in future products.

B. Implementation of Micro-Services for the Diagnosis Tool

Implementation was all exclusively conducted in Python, due to the vast implementation in data analytical contexts, using two essential auxiliary libraries: NumPy [23] (Version: 1.26.4) for the efficient numerical computations, particularly for array, matrix operations, and extensive mathematical functions, and Pandas [24] (Version: 2.2.2) for data manipulation and analysis, notably simplifying data filtering, grouping, and cleaning during the pre-processing steps. A SQLite database was integrated as the instance database for persistent local data within the micro-services to ensure reliability and prevent system failure and data loss. This choice provided a dependable data persistence solution.

Docker (Version: 0.17.3) [25] was utilized to containerize the micro-services, ensuring the technology process-level isolation, with the container operating in a separate process on the host system, preventing interference with other micro-services. This enhanced the reliability and predictability of the application and facilitated the deployment across the infrastructure environment, including the local production factory machines.

Into data collection terms, a Python-based *File-watcher micro-service* was utilized as the entry point of the AAS Type 2 that collects and standardize the data, after distributing to the other micro-services through a NATS [26] message broker using a publish-subscribe queue model.

C. Selection of the AI Algorithm for Quality Prediction

In this study, the Linear, Polynomial, Long Short Term Memory (Regressor), Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (Both with it integrated and not integrated module) regression algorithms were evaluated to forecast the quality metrics as a uni-variate time-series data gathered on the assembly line. Tests were held with a Intel Core i7-10510U Processor, 16 GBs of RAM and without a GPU to establish fairness between the algorithms. The Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (SMAPE) metric was chosen due to its normalization process ensuring a scale-independent performance comparison across the dataset. The key evaluation criteria included:

Table I: Car Quality: SMAPE % (Execution Time (s))

Algorithm	10 Samples	20 Samples	40 Samples	80 Samples
Linear	7.47 (0.00201)	6.25 (0.00201)	3.60 (0.00474)	7.01 (0.00769)
Polynomial	4.98 (0.00219)	16.54 (0.00100)	7.73 (0.00207)	5.90 (0.00301)
ARMA	4.16 (0.16026)	5.07 (0.27423)	5.20 (1.31564)	5.88 (6.74104)
ARIMA	11.36 (0.17130)	4.90 (0.27887)	5.88 (1.13678)	5.87 (6.49829)
LSTM	14.23 (14.17977)	9.65 (10.37179)	4.32 (13.26354)	6.29 (21.52445)

Table II: Measurement Quality: SMAPE % (Execution Time (s))

Algorithm	10 Samples	20 Samples	40 Samples	80 Samples
Linear	1.64 (0.00257)	3.55 (0.00140)	7.87 (0.00099)	5.37 (0.00102)
Polynomial	1.03 (0.00327)	4.23 (0.00200)	15.72 (0.00383)	9.43 (0.00200)
ARMA	0.94 (0.11717)	3.41 (0.23945)	4.92 (0.66962)	4.06 (3.49919)
ARIMA	1.09 (0.15660)	3.56 (0.26231)	5.70 (0.74012)	3.98 (3.94215)
LSTM	1.43 (9.89795)	9.32 (11.73306)	8.94 (13.90907)	4.08 (20.88681)

Table III: Car Quality: SMAPE % (Execution Time (s)) across Splits (Samples = 20)

Algorithm	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	Mean
Linear	6.25 (0.00146)	5.85 (0.00200)	3.87 (0.00101)	4.12 (0.00100)	9.77 (0.00118)	7.53 (0.00232)	6.57 (0.00150)
Polynomial	16.54 (0.00241)	14.90 (0.00253)	5.89 (0.00249)	18.98 (0.00352)	28.59 (0.00252)	11.08 (0.00295)	15.66 (0.00274)
ARMA	5.07 (0.31819)	5.70 (0.30059)	4.02 (0.32916)	4.06 (0.29736)	5.24 (0.30339)	7.61 (0.37472)	5.62 (0.32057)
ARIMA	4.90 (0.27645)	5.36 (0.30070)	3.42 (0.36483)	4.12 (0.31109)	5.00 (0.32753)	8.54 (0.32631)	5.56 (0.31782)
LSTM	8.83 (11.94624)	7.01 (11.59848)	7.62 (11.71460)	9.55 (12.38005)	5.03 (12.67552)	12.76 (11.97830)	8.80 (12.38287)

Table IV: Measurement Quality: SMAPE % (Execution Time (s)) across Splits (Samples = 20)

Algorithm	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	Mean
Linear	3.55 (0.00252)	10.16 (0.00100)	3.51 (0.00100)	3.48 (0.00100)	5.30 (0.00100)	3.61 (0.00151)	4.93 (0.00134)
Polynomial	4.23 (0.00289)	9.62 (0.00210)	13.08 (0.00200)	11.97 (0.00251)	9.93 (0.00200)	15.20 (0.00210)	10.67 (0.00227)
ARMA	3.35 (0.32527)	4.35 (0.25514)	4.73 (0.23374)	4.19 (0.26066)	3.12 (0.24889)	3.66 (0.23254)	3.90 (0.25937)
ARIMA	3.14 (0.08111)	3.12 (0.06697)	3.13 (0.08467)	3.15 (0.04566)	2.26 (0.05678)	4.23 (0.06629)	3.17 (0.06625)
LSTM	9.55 (10.34618)	4.36 (10.71273)	10.82 (10.25375)	7.23 (10.28507)	4.61 (11.05767)	9.52 (10.06574)	7.68 (10.45386)

- **Adaptability to Data Variability:** The manufacturing environment is highly variable, so algorithms with consistent error rates often outperform those with lower but erratic errors. As shown in Figure 9, the ARIMA model consistently tracked temporal trends and adapted to quality shifts, making it well-suited for a ZDM framework.
- **Prediction Accuracy:** The models were compared based on their ability to minimize overall forecasting errors, quantified using the SMAPE.
- **Training Time:** Given the dynamic nature of manufacturing data, fast retraining was essential to accommodate real-time updates. For this evaluation only the LSTM algorithm demonstrated a higher training time, but the rest handled easily the updates as new data became available.

Table I and Table II present one of several error comparisons for car-quality and measurement-quality predictions across four different sample sizes. The ARIMA algorithm consistently delivers a strong balance of low error rates and stable performance at each split. On the basis of the time vs error trade-off, we selected a sample size of 20 for further experiments, as it provided the most favorable combination of speed and accuracy.

Table III and Table IV, otherwise evaluated the regression algorithms using a cross-validation of 6 splits with 20 sam-

ples each, this yields a more reliable performance estimation by averaging results across multiple data splits. Finally the ARMA model was selected not only for its superior accuracy under the SMAPE metric but also for its operational efficiency and responsiveness in a live production setting. This selection underpins the diagnosis system’s ability to proactively identify deviations in product quality and supports timely proactive actions on the shop floor.

Fig. 9: Comparison of the Absolute Error for the Car Quality Regression Algorithms.

D. Assessing Prediction Optimizers Parameters

Following the selection of the regression algorithm, the next step involved the fine-tuning of the ARMA autoregression and moving average parameters to further reduce prediction errors. The autoregression parameter utilizes the previous quality values in the time series to predict the current observation. Essentially, it operates on the idea that past behavior is indicative of future behavior by assigning weighted coefficients to historical data points. On the other hand, the moving average component, focuses on modeling the error term: the difference between the predicted and actual values, by incorporating past forecast errors into the prediction. This renders the determination of the optimal parameter combination a particularly challenging task, especially in environments characterized by high-frequency data collection. The *Quality Prediction micro-service* was integrated with the *Prediction Optimizer micro-service* that assessed several metaheuristic parameter optimization techniques. Three optimizers were in this study namely the Colony Optimization Algorithm (ACO), the Bayesian Optimization and the Binary Grey Wolf Optimization (BGWO).

Figure 10 and Figure 11 present the SMAPE error comparisons for car quality and measurement quality before and after applying these optimization techniques.

Fig. 10: Car Quality Parameter Optimizer algorithm error comparison using SMAPE.

Fig. 11: Measurement Quality Parameter Optimizer algorithm error comparison using SMAPE.

The graphs revealed that while all optimizers contributed to a reduction in prediction errors, Bayesian Optimization

consistently offered a balanced approach between exploration and exploitation. In contrast, BGWO and ACO achieved faster convergence in specific parameter subspaces. The insights gained from the comparative analysis of the SMAPE between the raw and optimized ARMA models shown in the figures Figure 10 and Figure 11 underscored the importance of integrating an adaptive optimizer to enhance the ARMA regression model's performance. Also due to potential convergence issues caused by higher learning rates and the time-sensitive nature of the use case, the optimization algorithms were configured to terminate if convergence is not achieved within 60 seconds. In such instances, the algorithm returns the parameter set that attained the best combination along with its corresponding error rate.

This synergy between regression modeling and hyperparameter optimization within the micro-service simplification of choosing the most suitable optimization algorithm allowed the prediction system to achieve high-quality predictions (That can be observed in Figure 10 and Figure 11), ultimately contributed to the realization of a robust ZDM system.

E. Diagnosis Based on Prediction Results

After quality predictions are made, the *diagnosis and classification micro-service* gathers data from related systems and sends outputs in JSON format for the front-end visualization tool. The *diagnosis process* focuses on the evolution of predicted quality, offering a prognostic evaluation for proactive actions. Listing 1 shows an example of the *diagnosis tool* output for car and measurement quality predictions.

Listing 1 Car Diagnosis based on quality predictions.

```

1  {
2  "TIMESTAMP": "2024-04-04T04:05:30",
3  "DT_SOURCE": "measurement_station_2",
4  "ID": 7000000,
5  "DIAGNOSIS_TYPE": "PREDICT",
6  "DIAGNOSIS_OVERALL_RESULT": "APPROVED",
7  "DIAGNOSIS": {
8    "CONSEQUENCE": "Based on the last 20 cars the prediction model states that:
9                  The car quality will drop 10.0% and the measurement quality
10                 will raise 10.0% in 20 cars.",
11   "PROCESS_INDICATION": "The 17 car quality predicted was REJECTED by the
12                         current statistical model, please keep attention
13                         on car 7000017.",
14   "RESULT": "From the prediction the statistical model classified
15             12 as APPROVED, 3 as ATTENTION, 5 as REJECTED.
16             (Model mean: 0.86, Model standard deviation: 0.008)."

```

This JSON file represents a predictive diagnostic report from the "measurement_station_2" based in the last 20 cars until the ID 7000000. The overall result of the prediction namely classified by the Z-Score Based Classification model for this prediction was "APPROVED". The diagnosis includes insights based on the last 20 cars, indicating that car quality is expected to drop by 10%, while measurement quality may improve by 10% in the next 17 cars. This suggests a potential issue with consistency in car quality, despite the improving measurement quality.

Additionally, the system flags car ID 7000017 for special attention, as it is predicted to be rejected by the Z-Score Based Classification model. The prediction breakdown includes 12 approved cars, 3 requiring attention, and 5 rejected cars.

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed *diagnosis tool* stands out for its innovative characteristics, into the data transformation and quality metrics calculation methodology, but also into implementing an model re-training/self-learning mechanism for both the quality prediction variables, and for the Z-Score Classification models, also in order to solve the ambiguity in diagnosis systems, our work leverages a hybrid diagnosis system that combines real-time quality evaluation (Namely monitoring) with predictive analytics (Classification and Regression models) to realize the gaps in with the analyzed related work.

The evaluation of different AI-Regression models applied to a real-world study case yielded promising results, demonstrating its potential effectiveness in addressing useful knowledge about future industrial defects. Also, the whole system was developed in such way to support the adaptation to different use cases being highly parameterizable allowing effective handling of various limitations on the manufacturing environment, such as missing information, high-frequency and non-normalized data, to achieve a ZDM environment. The experimental validation supported the selection of the ARIMA algorithm combined with multiple optimization techniques and re-training every 20 data inputs. This strategy proved to be the most effective in high-frequency, unstable data scenarios, where the typical "train-once, test-many" approach is inadequate as data can change quickly.

Future work should be devoted to test different use cases with similar data formats such as deviation and thresholds data. In parallel, efforts will concentrate on optimizing resource utilization and overall performance in higher demanding domains. These enhancements aim to upgrade system operations and extend its applicability to a wider range of domains.

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